

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS AND FORMS OF IMPROVING THE SELF-EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: Currently, one of the main trends in the field of vocational education is the strengthening of the focus of the pedagogical process on enhancing independent work and preparing students for self-educational activities. The article reveals the problems of developing self-education competence among students, presents an understanding of the category of self-education, as well as pedagogical conditions.

Key words: self-education, pedagogical conditions, self-education competence, formation.

In modern society, continuous self-education is becoming one of the main conditions for the progress of human society, the world as a whole and, of course, a condition for the life success of an individual. Self-education is of particular importance in the context of lifelong learning, in which the main subject of planning, organizing, regulating and implementing education can only be the person himself, and the educational process develops into a process of self-education. Thus, in modern conditions, the need for selfeducation is caused, first of all, by the needs of society and the individual himself. At the same time, most students of higher educational institutions are not ready and do not know how to effectively organize the process of their selfeducation.

Therefore, in modern conditions, the problem of formation of students' self-educational competence and activation of independent work of university students is analyzed, the solution of which will contribute to improving the quality of training of future specialists in the context of globalization of education and increasing their competitiveness. By activation, we mean not just an increase in its volume, but an

increase in the effectiveness of independent work in achieving qualitatively new educational goals for the formation of students' professional competence and their readiness for self-educational activities. Readiness for self-educational activity is a personal quality expressed in the ability to relate the world of knowledge and the world of realities, in the ability to independently find answers to topical questions, based on the ability to freely navigate through various sources of information and critically analyze them. Readiness for self-educational activity is used in the meaning of a state or quality of personality characterized by knowledge of ways, forms and means of self-education, the ability to use them, as well as the corresponding state of the motivational sphere that determines the cognitive activity of a personality [1]. Self-educational activity is formed in the course of a lifetime. Its development is conditioned by internal personal prerequisites and external conditions. A favorable period for the development of self-educational activities is the period of study at a university, during which special attention should be paid to the development of search activity, independence and a creative approach to solving professional tasks. Students are the most active and active force in any country. The importance of beliefs and motives largely determines the needs and desires of students to form certain abilities that allow them to adapt to a changing world. As numerous studies show (Beznisko E. D., 2007; Zueva O. A., 2004; Chiknaverova K. G., 2016, etc.), the learning process at a university should involve the formation of students' independence, mobility, ability to use new educational technologies, and not only the transfer of as much knowledge as possible. To date, there are many interpretations of the concept of "competence of self-education" in the literature, based on the study of the phenomenon of self education, but its content is fragmentary and is determined by the scope of use of this concept. The most general idea of self-educational competence is due to the fact that it is an integrative property of a person, which is provided by a valuable and emotional attitude to self-educational activities and self-development, a set of knowledge about planning and implementing relevant activities and ways of selfeducation; experience in effectively solving problems of developing, developing and implementing models of preparation for self-education activities; readiness for permanent self-development professional qualities,

as well as self-improvement in the field of future professional activity (E. F. Zeer, 2005 [5]). According to E. A. Glukhova, the possibility of becoming a self-educational competence is realized at the stage of conscious incompetence, which may be due to the formation and manifestation of positive motives for self-education, personal readiness for it. The formation of competence is a transition from unconscious incompetence to conscious competence, and from it to unconscious competence (to skills brought to automatism) [7]. The formation of self-education competence in general is a process and result of the development of a student's personality under the influence of external factors and conditions, which does not have a final form and lasts throughout later life. The formation of self-education competence is of great importance in any kind of educational (project, research, creative) and professional activity, however, this problem is especially pronounced when the type of activity is in the initial stage of formation. According to E. S. Chebotareva, the competence of self-education is considered as an important professional quality, and therefore universities face the important task of defining and implementing special conditions and developing effective means of forming students' self-education competence. A specific goal in this case is the transition of the need for self-education in the context of the student's problems, his semantic sphere, into the basis for the development of personal experience [8].

The analysis of the formation of self-education competence conducted by K. G. Chiknaverova showed that this formation can be considered from the perspective of systemic, system-activity, competence-based, modular competencebased, personality-oriented and other approaches. Most vividly, in the author's opinion, the formation of self-education competence is presented from the position of axiological, competence-based, activity-based approaches as key ones that reflect the essential characteristics of the phenomenon under study.

Thus, within the framework of the axiological approach, the competence of self-education is defined as a value phenomenon that reflects the value attitude and personal significance of the future specialist to the activity of self-education. This approach is semantic, determining the direction of self-education, which is based on the need for

self-improvement and self-development of the student's personality. The competence-based approach involves the disclosure of the conditions for the formation and formation of key competencies, including self-educational, in the educational process, and also focuses on the development of these competencies.

The activity-based approach is a practice-oriented direction of studying the problem of formation of self-education competence among students [9].

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